

O‘ZBEKISTON TARIXI FANLARINI O‘QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada O‘zbekiston tarixi fanlarini o‘qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiya va noan‘anaviy ta‘lim metodlaridan umumli foydalanish masalalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: istiqbol, me‘morchilik, pedagogika, innovatsiya, pedagogik texnologiya

O‘zbekiston tarixi fanini o‘qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish o‘qitish sifatini yanada oshirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ushbu fanda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarga asoslangan o‘quv jarayonini tashkil qilishda elektron darsliklarga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda. Mavzularga oid tayyorlangan turli xil ko‘rgazmali vositalar, multimedia texnikalaridan foydalanish dars jarayonini yanada qiziqarli, aniq tushuncha hosil qilish va mavzuni oson o‘zlashtirishiga katta yordam beradi. Ko‘rgazmali vositalar (surat, plakat, reklama roliklari, kompyuter imitatsion modeli (animatsiya) va h.k) baynalmilal mohiyatga ega bo‘lib, ularni deyarli hamma tillarda foydalanish mumkin. Shu bilan birga, sohalarda erishilgan yutuqlarni auditoriya va auditoriyadan tashqari mashg‘ulotlarda targ‘ibot-tashviqot qilish orqali talaba yoshlar qalbi va ongiga tarix fanlarining mazmun-mohiyatini yanada chuqur o‘rganish imkoniyatlarini beradi. Ulug‘bek, Qozizoda Rumiy, Ali Qushchi, Jamshid Koshiy, Navoiy, Bekzod, Bobur singari ko‘plab ulug‘ ajdodlarimizning ijodiy faoliyatlari orqali yurtimiz ilmu-ma‘rifat, fan, adabiyot, me‘morchilikda jahon ahamiyatiga molik

yutuqlarga erishganini, Temuriylar davri Uygʻonish davri deb atalgani hamda uning mustaqil Oʻzbekiston istiqbolini belgilash, Oʻzbekiston xalqi tarixini shakllanishidagi ahamiyati ovoz va animatsiyalar yordamida yoritilib, dars jarayonlarini samaradorligini oshirmoqda. Talabalarning mazkur jarayonda faol ishtirokini taʼminlash maqsadida Oʻzbekiston tarixi faniga oid mavzular boʻyicha davra-suhbatlari, bahs-munozara, klaster (tarmoqlanish), kichik guruhlarda ishlash texnologiyalaridan foydalanish yaxshi samara beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, oʻzbekiston tarixi fanida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning qoʻllanishi qoʻyidagi natijalarga sabab boʻladi:

- talabalar mustaqil fikr bildirish koʻnikmasi shakllanadi ҳамда fanga qiziqishi yanada ortadi.
- egallanishi lozim boʻlgan tushunchalar mohiyatini oʻzlashtiradi;
- keltirilgan dalillarni asoslashga harakat qiladi va tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini yuksaltiradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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